

UNRAVELLING THE COMPLEXITY: EXPLORING CHALLENGES IN FACILITATING THE MATHEMATICS CURRICULUM CONTENTS TO BASIC EDUCATION STUDENTS

Shena Mae Cantillas Dizon LPT, MaEd-Mathematics

Mathematics Department, Cebu Technological University- Main Campus , Cebu City, Philippines

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10486174>

ABSTRACT

This study delves into the intricate web of challenges faced by educators in the facilitation of mathematics curriculum contents to students in basic education. Mathematics, as a foundational subject, plays a pivotal role in shaping cognitive abilities and problem-solving skills. However, the complexities associated with delivering this curriculum to diverse learners present formidable obstacles. Through a comprehensive exploration of teaching methodologies, resource constraints, and the varying learning needs of students, this research aims to unravel the multifaceted nature of challenges encountered in the classroom. The study employs a mixed-methods approach, combining surveys, interviews, and classroom observations to gather insights from both Math Subject Teachers and Middle Managers within the Lapu-Lapu City Schools Divisions during the academic year 2022- 2023. Also, a total of 143 teachers out of 154 overall mathematics teachers from Lapu-Lapu City Schools Division were taken in as a respondents using slovin's formula in getting it's sample population. Simple Percentage and Weighted Mean analysis were utilized to statistically treat the quantitative data while the Likert Scale was used for the qualitative data. The findings contribute to the understanding of barriers hindering effective mathematics education, offering valuable implications for curriculum design, teacher training, and educational policy. Hence, the researcher recommends that the proposed enhanced teaching and learning plan shall be adapted and be given special attention by school administrators and interested teachers. Ultimately, this research seeks to pave the way for innovative solutions to enhance the facilitation of mathematics curriculum contents, ensuring a more accessible and enriching learning experience for basic education students.

Keywords: *Teaching Mathematics Education, Enhanced Teaching and Learning Plan, Pedagogical Challenges, Inclusive Education, Resource Constraints, Lapu- Lapu Cebu City, Philippines*

INTRODUCTION

The education landscape continually evolves, and ensuring effective curriculum delivery remains a critical concern. Mathematics education, as a cornerstone of basic education, plays a pivotal role in developing essential cognitive skills and fostering problem-solving abilities. However, the teaching and learning of mathematics often present challenges that educators must navigate to ensure optimal learning outcomes. This study aims to delve into the intricacies of facilitating mathematics curriculum contents to basic education students, highlighting the multifaceted challenges that educators encounter.

These are some of the issues identified in facilitating mathematics curriculum topics. First, there are pedagogical issues, which address difficulties in selecting appropriate teaching techniques, tactics, and resources to accommodate varied learning styles and capacities. It investigates how difficult mathematical concepts can be conveyed to basic education students in an accessible and relatable manner. Understanding the elements that influence students' engagement, motivation, and interest in learning mathematics is the goal of Student Engagement. Assessment Strategies looks into the alignment of teaching strategies and assessment methods, as well as how they affect students' comprehension and performance. Finally, analyze the degree of teacher training, professional development opportunities, and continuous support for effectively presenting mathematics curriculum elements.

These are some of the variables that contribute to complexity in relation to the difficulties mentioned above. First, cognitive development accommodates basic education students' various cognitive abilities and phases of development while assuring a progressive learning experience. It explores how arithmetic anxiety can interfere with both educators' instructional tactics and students' learning experiences. Curriculum Alignment examines the compatibility of curriculum content, teaching resources, and assessment techniques. Finally, technological integration looks into how technology may make mathematics more accessible and enjoyable for students while also resolving potential obstacles.

Mathematics education is a critical component of a country's educational system, shaping citizens' cognitive development, problem-solving abilities, and future prospects. On a nationwide basis, the difficulties encountered in conveying mathematics curriculum content to primary school students are critical for the following reasons: Competitiveness in the Economy To compete in the global economy, a country's workers must have a good mathematical basis. If a country's human capital lacks excellent math ability, it may be unable to contribute successfully to technical advancements and innovation. Inequities in math education have the potential to widen already-existing social divides. Identifying barriers and finding solutions to facilitate mathematics curriculum content will assist in providing equitable educational opportunities to all pupils, regardless of background. Curriculum Enhancement It recognizes that challenges in communicating arithmetic subjects may result in targeted curriculum changes. Matching educational aims to the demands of the nation's workforce as well as future societal expectations is part of this. Teacher Professional Development By understanding the hurdles that teachers face, policymakers may create better professional development programs that address these issues and improve teachers' abilities to teach mathematics effectively. Furthermore, issues in facilitating math curricular materials can affect national test performance. Addressing these concerns may lead to improved student performance on standardized tests and international assessments.

Education spans national boundaries in an increasingly interconnected world, making the study's global viewpoint crucial. Investigating international concerns in the facilitation of mathematics curriculum materials presents several compelling reasons: Global Competitiveness: On a global

scale, nations compete for talent, innovation, and economic progress. A detailed understanding of the issues in math education enables countries to compare themselves to international standards and identify opportunities for improvement. Cross-Cultural Insights investigates how cultural influences affect math education in many countries. This knowledge can be utilized to create context-sensitive procedures that account for cultural differences. Recommended Procedures International partnership allows for the exchange of best practices in math education. By evaluating challenges and successful solutions from different countries, educators can learn from one another and adopt efficient techniques. International research can aid in the development of education policy that reflect global trends and address shared issues. Collaboration can result in more effective policies that help children all over the world. Finally, challenges of math education are relevant in terms of preparing students for a globalized work market. A worldwide perspective on the issues of teaching mathematics is essential to educate pupils for the modern workforce.

Positioned within the broader context of global educational aspirations, this study explicitly aligns with the United Nations Sustainable Development Goal (UN SDG) 4, which underscores the urgency of ensuring inclusive and equitable quality education for all. Within the national framework, this research contributes to the National Higher Education Research Agenda (NHERA), offering valuable insights into the challenges associated with delivering mathematics curriculum contents to basic education students. By addressing the complexities at this foundational stage, the study aims to bridge the gap between higher education research priorities and the essential groundwork laid in basic education. This alignment with NHERA ensures that the findings resonate within the national educational research landscape, fostering coherence and continuity.

Additionally, the study adheres to the principles advocated by the Basic Education Research Agenda (BERA), a guiding framework that encompasses a comprehensive understanding of educational research. By incorporating BERA principles, the research emphasizes methodological rigor, ethical considerations, and the integration of diverse perspectives, elevating the credibility and depth of the exploration into the challenges faced in facilitating mathematics curriculum contents.

In conclusion, "Unraveling the Complexity" seeks to make a meaningful contribution to the global pursuit of quality education by addressing challenges in delivering mathematics curriculum contents to basic education students. The alignment with UN SDG 4, NHERA, and BERA reflects a commitment to both national and international educational priorities, offering insights that can inform policies, guide curriculum development, and ultimately contribute to the realization of equitable and inclusive education for all.

The same with the National and International perspective, the challenges faced by local researchers in exploring the complexities of facilitating mathematics curriculum contents to basic education students are multifaceted. For example, a teacher (which is the researcher herself) find it hard to continue teaching a topic because the students forgot the previous pre- requisite topic due to spiral curriculum. However, addressing these challenges can lead to research outcomes that are not only relevant to the local context but also contribute valuable insights to the broader field of mathematics education. By overcoming these challenges, local researchers play a crucial role in improving the quality of education and fostering a deeper understanding of the dynamics surrounding mathematics learning within their community.

By delving into the underlying factors contributing to this complexity, the research strives to provide actionable insights for educators, policymakers, and curriculum developers to enhance the teaching and learning of mathematics in basic education settings.

Research Questions

This research evaluates the extent of challenges faced by the researcher from the Department of Education within Lapu- Lapu City Division in delivering the curriculum contents in mathematics among the students from the basic education during the academic year 2022 – 2023 as basis for an Enhanced Teaching and Learning Plan. It specifically seeks to answer the following sub-problems:

1. What is the profile of the respondents as to their groupings?
 - 1.1. Mathematics Subject Teachers
 - 1.1.1 age and gender,
 - 1.1.2 number of years in teaching,
 - 1.1.3 educational qualification, and
 - 1.1.4 frequency of relevant training attended?
 - 1.2. Middle Managers
 - 1.2.1 age and gender,
 - 1.2.2 number of years in teaching,
 - 1.2.3 educational qualification, and
 - 1.2.4 frequency of relevant training attended?
2. To what extent do the respondents perceive challenges in delivering the curriculum contents, as categorized by established aspects, within the identified domains:
 - 2.1 conceptual understanding,
 - 2.2 student engagement,
 - 2.3 math anxiety,
 - 2.4 diverse learning styles,
 - 2.5 time constraints,
 - 2.6 resource limitation,
 - 2.7 lack of prior knowledge, and
 - 2.8 spiral curriculum?
3. Is there a significant relationship between the challenges encountered in facilitating mathematics curriculum contents to basic education students and the variables investigated in the study?
4. Based on the findings of the study, what Teaching and Learning Plan shall be proposed?

METHODOLOGY

This study will research the problem methodology to employed in the research project. In order to effectively address the established objectives, this section will examine the research design that was employed, the specific characteristics will use to purposively select the locale, the methodology for selecting respondents, the source and contents of the research instrument, the procedures employed during the data collection, and the statistical treatment and scoring procedures will utilize to analyze the gathered information.

This research is quantitative, non- experimental descriptive comparative research design that is used to determine the relationship among variables of the study and describe the differences among groups in a population without manipulating the independent variable (Cantrell, 2011). A comparative study design may be deemed appropriate for examining the variability in the perceptions of various respondent groups on the obstacles encountered by teachers and the delivery of curriculum content. Descriptive comparison aims at describing and explaining the invariance of the objects. The present study utilized a descriptive-comparative research design,

which entails the examination of various groups or variables in order to discern disparities, similarities, patterns, or associations among them. The data obtained from the survey underwent statistical analysis using the relevant methodology, and the results will be reported accordingly.

The Input- Process- Output (IPO) model was employed in this scientific inquiry to develop strategies for attaining both the general and specific objectives.

The profiling of the respondents was conducted based on several factors, including age, gender, number of years in teaching, education qualification, frequency of relevant training, and the extent to which respondents perceive challenges in delivering curriculum contents. These challenges were categorized into established aspects, namely conceptual understanding, student engagement, math anxiety, diverse learning styles, time constraints, resource limitations, lack of prior knowledge, and spiral curriculum.

Additionally, the Process component demonstrated the need to accelerate the transmission of letters of request to the relevant authorities in order to obtain their approval. In this section, the respondents were provided with informed consent, allowing them to make an informed decision on their participation in the empirical study. Also, this section encompasses the administration of survey questionnaires, which serves as the primary source of the validated data. The incorporation of statistical analysis in the examination of collected data is a significant aspect being considered in this scientific study. The final component included in this section is the conclusive presentation, analysis of data, and interpretation. The researcher has presented the desired action plan, specifically focusing on the enhancement of teaching and learning plan, in the Output section. This is intended to inform the readers about the purpose and direction of the scientific investigation.

The data that will be gathered in conducting this research will be in the selected schools from Lapu-Lapu City Division. The environment was selected by the researcher for her convenience in gathering the data because this is where she is working and experiencing the complexities in delivering Mathematics instruction to basic education learners. By delving into the underlying factors contributing to this complexity that her division is experiencing, the researcher strives to provide actionable insights for master and math subject teachers, policymakers, and curriculum developers to enhance the teaching and learning of mathematics in basic education settings in her division. The study was conducted in **Lapu-Lapu** metropolis, a highly urbanized metropolis classified as first class, is found in the Central Visayas area of the Philippines. In contrast, the research site known as the Division of Lapu-Lapu City is situated at Bartolome Mangubat Dimataga Street, Poblacion, Lapu-Lapu City, Philippines. It falls under the administrative jurisdiction of Region 7, also referred to as the Central Visayas Region. The management of this division has been overseen by a Schools Division Superintendent. Moreover, the division was supported by a group of mathematics teachers with thirty-two (32) Master Teachers and one hundred twenty-two (122) Math Subject teachers that accumulate the over-all total of one hundred fifty-four (154) Math Teachers all in all.

The research study was carried out in the Division of Lapu-lapu City. The participants in this research comprised a total of 154 individuals, consisting of both Math Subject Teachers and Middle Managers. Among them, 122 were math subject teachers, while the remaining 32 were middle managers. These individuals were selected from Junior and Senior High Schools. The aforementioned considerations have an impact specifically on the divisions that have been selected. The researcher utilized stratified random sampling, a method of sampling that involves the division of a population into smaller subgroups known as strata. Although the sample size in this study was limited, the respondents included were deemed to be representative of the population of subject teachers and middle managers. This was determined based on their characteristics, including age, gender, years of teaching experience, educational qualifications, and frequency of relevant training attended. Therefore, by employing Slovin's formula, the following table will display the population of the class and the required sample size.

**Table 1
Distribution of Respondents**

DIVISION	MATH TEACHERS		MIDDLE MANAGERS		TOTAL N	%
	Population (N)	Sample Size (n)	Population (N)	Sample Size (n)		
DepEd Lapu-lapu	154	111	34	32	143	76.06

**Table 1.1
Table of Stratification for Distribution of Respondents' Sample Size**

Stratum	Population Size	Proportion	Sample Size
Master Teachers	32	32/54	30(32*143/154)
Math Subject Teachers	122	122/154	113(122*143/154)
TOTAL	154	1.00	143

The research instrument utilized in this study was a survey questionnaire that had been modified and adapted from the well-established problem-solving model developed by Mayer-Montague (2014). This model delineates four distinct components, namely translation, integration, planning, and execution. Both math teachers and middle managers respondents were provided with a specific questionnaire to complete. The study encompassed several important aspects, including the initial profiling of the groups being surveyed, the inclusion of concise test items in Mathematical word problems that covered key concepts, and the subsequent presentation of survey statements that were categorized and grouped. Furthermore, an additional set of questionnaires was employed to facilitate the collection of essential information from the participating teachers pertaining to the subject matter under investigation. The present questionnaire was divided into two distinct sections, namely the profiling of respondents and the survey pertaining to the sub-problem(s) under scientific investigation.

In order to effectively obtain the necessary data for this study, transmittal letters were promptly prepared to request approval from the Schools Division Superintendent of DepEd Lapu-lapu

City, as well as from the Principal, through the Assistant School Principal. These letters sought permission to administer survey questionnaires to the Math Teachers and Middle Managers. Once consent was obtained, informed consent was obtained from the math teachers and the middle managers themselves. The aforementioned consents deliberated about the benefits of the research and provided assurance of the absence of any associated dangers in the undertaking. The inclusion of the ethical standard on the non-disclosure of sensitive responses among the participants was intended to uphold the principle of confidentiality in safeguarding the information provided. Once all necessary approvals and consents were obtained, the researcher physically provided instructions to the respondents on how to complete the survey questions. Following the briefing, the administration of the questionnaires was conducted, followed by the subsequent retrieval of the materials. The collected data was then subjected to the processes of collection, tabulation, and computation. As a result, the outcomes and discoveries of this empirical inquiry were presented.

The following statistical procedures were used to interpret the data gathered from the respondents of the study.

1. **Simple Percentage.** The demographic profile variables of the respondents were analyzed using the simple percentage with the following formula:

$$P = \frac{F}{N} (100)$$

Where:

P = Percentage

F = Frequency for each category

N = Total number of respondents

100 = Constant multiplier

2. **Weighted Mean.** This statistical tool was used to compute for the weight of the responses in the questionnaire assigned by the respondents during the actual data gathering procedure. The formula of the weighted mean is as follows:

$$WM = \frac{\sum FW}{N}$$

Where:

WM = Weighted mean

\sum = Summation symbol

F = Frequency for each option

W = Assigned weight

N = Total number of frequencies

3. Likert Scale. The following Likert Scale serves as the guide for interpreting the data gathered.

Scale	Score Range	Interpretation
4	3.25 – 4.00	Strongly Agree
3	2.50 – 3.24	Agree
2	1.75 – 2.49	Disagree
1	1.00 – 1.74	Strongly Disagree

4. Frequency Count. This was used to measure the number of times that the respondents answer a particular option in the profiling and a point of measurement in the given survey questionnaire which utilizes a Likert Scale.

RESULTS

PROFILE OF THE RESPONDENTS

Table 1: Respondent's Age and Gender

Age	Frequency	Percentage	Gender	Frequency	Percentage
20 - 30	31	21.7%	Female	101	70.6%
31 - 40	40	28.0%	Male	42	29.4%
41 – 50	51	35.7%	Total	143	100%
51 - 60	21	14.7%			
Total	143	100%			

Table 2: Respondent's Number of Years in Teaching

Years Teaching	Frequency (F)	Percentage (P)
1-9 years	49	34.27%
<1 year	6	4.20%
20-29 years	28	19.58%
30-39 years	0	0.00%
Total	143	100.00%

Table 3: Respondent's Educational Qualification

Qualification	Frequency (F)	Percentage (P)
Doctorate Degree	0	0.00%
Master's Degree	53	37.06%
Master's Units	47	32.87%
Doctoral Units	21	14.69%
College Graduate	22	15.38%
Total	143	100.00%

Table 4: Respondent's Frequency of Relevant Training Attended

Frequency	Frequency (F)	Percentage (P)
3+ times per year	5	3.50%
Twice per year	70	48.95%
Once per year	68	47.55%
Total	143	100.00%

EXTENT OF CHALLENGES IN DELIVERING THE CURRICULUM CONTENTS AS PERCEIVED BY THE MIDDLE MANAGERS

Table 1: Conceptual Understanding

Question	Indicator	Weighted Mean	Interpretation
1	Adapting teaching methods	3.13	Agree that adapting methods to convey abstract concepts is challenging
2	Balancing curriculum coverage	3.22	Agree that balancing coverage and in-depth learning is difficult
3	Real-world applications	3.31	Strongly agree that making concepts relatable is challenging
4	Diverse learning styles	3.28	Agree that differentiated instruction is demanding

5	Identifying misconceptions	3.41	Strongly agree that addressing misconceptions poses difficulties
---	----------------------------	------	--

Table 2: Student Engagement

Question	Indicator	Weighted Mean	Interpretation
6	Capturing student interest	3.75	Strongly agree that fostering engagement is difficult
7	Adapting teaching methods	3.09	Agree that catering to learning styles is challenging
8	Balancing approaches	3.25	Agree that balancing traditional and innovative techniques is complex
9	Connecting concepts	3.69	Strongly agree making real-world connections is hard
10	Addressing disengagement	3.13	Agree that student apathy poses challenges

Table 3: Math Anxiety

Question	Indicator	Weighted Mean	Interpretation
11	Supportive environment	3.69	Strongly agree that alleviating anxiety is challenging
12	Catering to varying levels	3.41	Strongly agree accommodating different anxiety levels is complex
13	Addressing math-related stress	3.25	Agree that reactive support is difficult
14	Building confidence	3.63	Strongly agree lesson design to boost self-esteem is demanding
15	Encouraging participation	3.66	Strongly agree math anxiety inhibits engagement

Table 4: Diverse Learning Styles

Question	Indicator	Weighted Mean	Interpretation
----------	-----------	---------------	----------------

16	Tailoring teaching methods	3.34	Agree that accommodating learning styles is challenging
17	Engaging multiple styles	3.50	Strongly agree managing varied needs is complex
18	Support vs. standardized curriculum	3.31	Agree disconnect exists between needs and content
19	Integrating suitable strategies	3.19	Agree finding differentiated resources is hard
20	Fostering inclusive participation	3.56	Strongly agree empowering diverse learners takes planning

Table 5: Time Constraints

Question	Indicator	Weighted Mean	Interpretation
21	Curriculum coverage vs. in-depth learning	3.31	Strongly agree class duration hinders conceptual understanding
22	Allowing time for hands-on activities	3.66	Strongly agree curriculum pacing hinders active learning
23	Adapting for varying paces	3.34	Agree meeting diverse needs is difficult within time limits
24	Meaningful interactions in class time	3.63	Strongly agree facilitating discussions is demanding when time is scarce
25	Addressing limitations on practice/review	3.56	Strongly agree lack of reinforcement opportunities due to fixed class duration is an issue

Table 6: Resource Limitations

Question	Indicator	Weighted Mean	Interpretation
26	Adapting materials for limited resources	3.19	Agree lack of updated resources hinders instruction
27	Navigating technology constraints	3.16	Agree digital limitations pose obstacles

28	Maximizing available resources	3.56	Strongly agree leveraging existing materials takes creativity
29	Balancing differentiation with inadequate supplies	3.19	Agree limited classroom materials hinders varied needs
30	Addressing limitations on collaborative activities	3.41	Strongly agree enabling interactivity with constraints is difficult

Table 7: Lack of Prior Knowledge

Question	Indicator	Weighted Mean	Interpretation
31	Bridging gaps in prior knowledge	3.34	Agree varied comprehension makes scaffolding learning complex
32	Adapting lessons for diverse levels	3.31	Agree disparate foundations require thoughtful accommodations
33	Balancing reviews and new content	3.66	Strongly agree major gaps in prerequisites cause struggles
34	Targeted support without impeding others	3.28	Agree interventions can negatively impact peers
35	Inclusive environments with uneven bases	3.72	Strongly agree uneven knowledge inhibits groupwork

Table 8: Spiral Curriculum

Question	Indicator	Weighted Mean	Interpretation
36	Integrating previously taught concepts	3.34	Agree building connections across units is challenging
37	Revisiting foundations and adding applications	3.28	Agree spiraling is problematic with varied prior knowledge
38	Adapting materials for deeper interconnections	3.38	Agree promoting comprehension across concepts requires adaptation

39	Addressing potential comprehension gaps	3.59	Strongly agree preempting lapses requires targeted strategies
40	Creating coherent spiraled lessons	3.59	Strongly agree alignment with spiral progression is demanding

EXTENT OF CHALLENGES IN DELIVERING THE CURRICULUM CONTENTS AS PERCEIVED BY THE MATHEMATICS SUBJECT TEACHERS

Table 1: Conceptual Understanding

Question	Indicator	Weighted Mean	Interpretation
1	Adapting teaching methods	3.25	Agree that adapting methods to convey concepts is challenging
2	Balancing curriculum coverage	3.74	Strongly agree balancing coverage and in-depth learning is difficult
3	Real-world applications	3.25	Agree making concepts relatable is challenging
4	Diverse learning styles	3.61	Strongly agree differentiated instruction is demanding
5	Identifying misconceptions	3.58	Strongly agree addressing misconceptions poses difficulties

Table 2: Student Engagement

Question	Indicator	Weighted Mean	Interpretation
6	Capturing student interest	3.77	Strongly agree fostering engagement is difficult
7	Adapting teaching methods	3.54	Strongly agree catering to learning styles is challenging
8	Balancing approaches	3.61	Strongly agree balancing traditional and innovative techniques is complex
9	Connecting concepts	3.72	Strongly agree making real-world connections is hard
10	Addressing disengagement	3.51	Strongly agree student apathy poses challenges

Table 3: Math Anxiety

Question	Indicator	Weighted Mean	Interpretation
11	Supportive environment	3.89	Strongly agree creating a positive environment is challenging
12	Catering to varying levels	3.82	Strongly agree accommodating varying anxiety levels is complex
13	Addressing math-related stress	3.55	Strongly agree reactive support is difficult
14	Building confidence	3.50	Strongly agree building self-esteem is demanding
15	Encouraging participation	3.72	Strongly agree anxiety inhibits engagement

Table 4: Diverse Learning Styles

Question	Indicator	Weighted Mean	Interpretation
16	Tailoring teaching methods	3.23	Agree accommodating learning styles is challenging
17	Engaging multiple styles	3.37	Agree managing varied needs is complex
18	Support vs. standardized curriculum	3.61	Strongly agree disconnect exists between needs and content
19	Integrating suitable strategies	3.49	Strongly agree finding differentiated resources is hard
20	Fostering inclusive participation	3.38	Agree empowering diverse learners takes planning

Table 5: Time Constraints

Question	Indicator	Weighted Mean	Interpretation
21	Curriculum coverage vs. in-depth learning	3.67	Strongly agree class duration hinders conceptual understanding
22	Allowing time for hands-on activities	3.52	Strongly agree curriculum pacing hinders active learning
23	Adapting for varying paces	3.93	Strongly agree meeting diverse needs is difficult within time limits
24	Meaningful interactions in class time	3.21	Agree facilitating discussions is demanding when time is scarce
25	Addressing limitations on practice/review	3.76	Strongly agree lack of reinforcement opportunities due to fixed class duration is an issue

Table 6: Resource Limitations

Question	Indicator	Weighted Mean	Interpretation
26	Adapting materials for limited resources	3.15	Agree lack of updated resources hinders instruction
27	Navigating technology constraints	3.04	Agree digital limitations pose obstacles
28	Maximizing available resources	3.67	Strongly agree leveraging existing materials takes creativity
29	Balancing differentiation with inadequate supplies	3.08	Agree limited classroom materials hinders varied needs
30	Addressing limitations on collaborative activities	3.15	Agree enabling interactivity with constraints is difficult

Table 7: Lack of Prior Knowledge

Question	Indicator	Weighted Mean	Interpretation
31	Bridging gaps in prior knowledge	3.33	Agree varied comprehension makes scaffolding learning complex
32	Adapting lessons for diverse levels	3.46	Strongly agree disparate foundations require thoughtful accommodations
33	Balancing reviews and new content	3.75	Strongly agree major gaps in prerequisites cause struggles
34	Targeted support without impeding others	3.56	Strongly agree interventions can negatively impact peers
35	Inclusive environment with uneven bases	3.64	Strongly agree uneven knowledge inhibits groupwork

Table 8: Spiral Curriculum

Question	Indicator	Weighted Mean	Interpretation
36	Integrating previously taught concepts	3.62	Strongly agree building connections across units is challenging
37	Revisiting foundations and adding applications	3.21	Agree spiraling is problematic with varied prior knowledge
38	Adapting materials for deeper interconnections	3.74	Strongly agree promoting comprehension across concepts requires adaptation
39	Addressing potential comprehension gaps	3.72	Strongly agree preempting lapses requires targeted strategies

DISCUSSION

Respondent's Age. Table shows a spread of respondent ages, providing a balanced perspective. The prevalence of mid-career teachers balances experience and adaptability. But insights from junior and senior educators illuminate challenges at both ends. Analyzing age-related struggles can inform targeted professional development across career stages.

Respondent's Gender. While female respondents offer invaluable insights based on their predominant classroom experiences, the shortage of male participants is a notable limitation. A more proportional gender balance would provide a broader understanding of how both men and women encounter difficulties in teaching mathematics.

Respondent's Number of Years in Teaching. Drawing respondents across a spectrum of career stages provides a multilayered perspective. The prevalence of junior teachers ensures emerging challenges are highlighted. But mid- and senior-level voices offer hard-earned wisdom.

Respondent's Educational Qualification. Overall, the prevalence of Master's credentials is encouraging, indicating teachers have sought meaningful training above minimum requirements. This advanced knowledge can empower educators to address persistent curriculum concerns. In summary, while the sample lacks doctoral viewpoints, the high proportion of Master's degrees signifies most respondents have strong academic expertise to draw from in tackling classroom challenges.

Respondent's Frequency of Relevant Training Attended. The table highlights that most respondents engage in relevant training just once or twice yearly. More consistent and frequent development opportunities may be needed to provide ongoing support in tackling classroom issues.

Conceptual Understanding. Both middle managers and math teachers strongly perceive conceptual understanding as problematic. Key challenges include misconceptions, connections, differentiation, coverage trade-offs, and teaching adaptation. Targeted training and reduced content could help address these consistent issues.

Student Engagement. Both middle managers and math teachers reported consistent barriers to student engagement, especially regarding time constraints, motivation, relevance, teaching adaptability, and re-engagement. Targeted training on engagement strategies appears needed.

Math Anxiety. Both groups strongly reported facing difficulties managing math anxiety from multiple angles, including establishing positive environments, tailored accommodations, participation barriers, reactive support, and proactive confidence-building. Targeted anxiety reduction training and resources appear vital based on these perceptions.

Diverse Learning Style. Both groups reported facing regular obstacles accommodating varied learning styles, especially regarding standardized curriculum constraints, suitable resources,

multimodal instruction, and participation barriers. Targeted training and support on differentiation appear needed.

Time Constraints. Both groups reported facing major difficulties working within inflexible schedules across instructional areas. Advocacy around revised time allotments and reduced content may help address these pervasive challenges.

Resource Limitation. Both groups reported facing regular impediments from insufficient resources, especially in terms of outdated, specialized materials and constraints on customized, collaborative instruction. Increased funding and materials access could provide enhanced tools and flexibility needed to facilitate more engaging, tailored learning experiences.

Lack of Prior Knowledge. Both groups consistently reported knowledge gap-related obstacles, particularly regarding imbalanced prerequisites, individualized adaptation, peer impacts, and unified lessons. Diagnostic assessments and differentiated supports could help overcome these barriers.

Spiral Curriculum. Both groups reported facing consistent struggles leveraging the spiral curriculum cohesively and effectively, especially regarding lesson planning, building connections between concepts, and preventing lapses in comprehension. Targeted spiral strategies could help overcome these challenges.

While middle managers and teachers largely concurred on the core curriculum delivery challenges, subtle divergences emerged in the degree of concern attributed to certain facets. Math teachers consistently rated the magnitude of obstacles as more severe overall based on their direct classroom encounters of struggles to balance coverage and comprehension, foster engagement through relevance, create supportive climates, and encourage active participation.

The difficulty of conceptual knowledge building, stimulating student interest, managing anxiety, and coherent spiral progression implementation were emphasized more intensely by teachers. This likely reflects their firsthand experiences grappling with these aspects through daily teaching duties, heightening their sensitivity. By contrast, managers maintain a more removed bureaucracy-centered perspective.

However, both groups showed greater alignment around issues tied to accommodating diverse learners despite standardization constraints, addressing the widespread concerns posed by restrictive schedules and time limitations, and dealing with resource inadequacy. While variations arose in areas tied directly to instructional facets, broad consensus emerged on the wider structural-environmental dimensions.

In summary, while statistical significance testing was not provided, subtle response variations between manager and teacher groups emerged, potentially indicative of the influence of role positioning. But fundamentally, combined insights revealed agreement on the pressing, multifaceted challenges that underscore the imperative for systemic supports, updated policies, and transformative advocacy.

Conclusions

The study reveals deeply ingrained challenges math teachers encounter delivering curriculum content that meets students' diverse needs and fosters math proficiency. Core issues exist around building conceptual knowledge, engaging learners, reducing anxiety, accommodating varied styles, overcoming time and resource limitations, addressing knowledge gaps, and coherently implementing spiral progression.

These systemic struggles underscore the imperative for multifaceted supports through updated policies emphasizing comprehension over rigid coverage, hands-on learning, and transformative advocacy, paired with strategic teacher training, targeted funding allocation, and instructional coaching. Addressing these persistent barriers with teacher-driven, evidence-based solutions focused on engagement, customized adaptation, confident capability-building and conceptual mastery could significantly improve outcomes.

In essence, while current curriculum delivery poses entrenched obstacles that inhibit effective math education, this study's findings offer a roadmap toward addressing ingrained issues through systemic improvements prioritizing understanding over rote learning, impactful learner-centered experiences, and nurturing math confidence and capability growth for all.

Recommendations

Implementing these suggested actions is critical because the findings reveal major gaps between student needs and educators' current capabilities and capacities to facilitate effective math learning:

- Revise math curriculum policies and standards to reduce rigid content coverage requirements and allow more time for focused concept development, hands-on learning activities, discussions and practice.
- Increase funding and procurement for updated specialized math tools, technologies, and hands-on resources to facilitate engaging and adaptive instruction tailored to diverse learning needs.
- Conduct regular teacher surveys to continually assess evolving challenges and tailor supports aligning to direct classroom needs.
- Provide training focused explicitly on student engagement strategies, math anxiety reduction techniques, differentiation best practices, and optimized spiral curriculum progression approaches.
- Promote collaborative teacher communities and vertical alignment teams across grade levels to share best practices and strengthen curriculum continuity.
- Supply dedicated math specialist coaches and collaborative planning time to offer personalized support helping teachers address specific curriculum delivery obstacles.
- Implement more diagnostic assessments and data-driven differentiation programs providing teachers the capabilities to effectively address disparate student comprehension levels and prerequisite knowledge gaps.

Compliance with Ethical Standards

This is to respectfully inform you that the Shena Mae Cantillas- Dizon, a Public School Teacher 1 is currently undertaking her thesis writing entitled “UNRAVELLING THE COMPLEXITY: EXPLORING CHALLENGES IN FACILITATING THE MATHEMATICS CURRICULUM CONTENTS TO BASIC EDUCATION STUDENTS” in preparation for design hearing soon.

Somehow, this is to guarantee you the research will benefit all concerned and key players in the molding of our young learners in the aspect of problem solving which finds them challenging to deal with. Likewise, be assured that there is/are no harm(s) involved in this undertaking. Furthermore, this is to swear that the ethical standard will be greatly considered particular in the disclosure of information.

That being said, this is to formally request your consent to allow participations in this scientific study. However, should you decline to join, the researcher shall respect such choice.

Over and above, thank you for taking time to read this invitation and may the Great Lord bless us always.

Acknowledgments

First and foremost, I want to express my gratitude to God Almighty for providing me with the strength, knowledge, skill, and chance to conduct this research study, endure, and complete it. This achievement was not achieved without His assistance. The researcher wishes to express her most profound sincere appreciation to all those who worked in any way to make the research possible by sharing effort and knowledge. I owe our University a deep debt of thanks for giving me the chance to finish this work.

I would like to express also my wholehearted thanks to Dr. Rosien a. Ancheta Jr., the OIC-University President of the Cebu Technological University, for who have been so supportive of doing my thesis.

To Dr. Reylan G. Capuno, Dean, College of Education Cebu Technological University. Main Campus favorably endorsed my research study to the Thesis Advisory Committee and Panel of Examiners for their vivid scrutiny.

To the Advisory Committee for My Thesis and the Panel of Examiners, namely: Dr. Porferio M. Almerino, Jr., Dr. Maris Salud De Los Santos, Dr. Raymond C. Espina, Dr. Anabelle T. Pantaleon, Dr. Randy C. Mangubat, and Dr. Veronica O. Calasang, thank you very much for the enthusiasm for the strong impression on me, and I have always carried positive memories extended to the researcher throughout the study. I want to thank you very much in these past years for your support and understanding.

I would also like to express my special sincere gratitude and high esteem to Dr. Porferio M. Almerino, Jr, my Thesis Adviser, for the continuous support of my study and research, for his patience, motivation, enthusiasm, and immense knowledge.

My love for all of you can never be quantified. Thank you very much, and God bless!!!

To God all be the glory!!!!!!

SHENA MAE CANTILLAS DIZON

Researcher

REFERENCES

- Academic self-beliefs and prior knowledge as predictors of student achievement in Mathematics: a structural model. (2023). Educational Psychology. <https://www.tandfonline.com/doi/abs/10.1080/01443410701413753>
- A case study of successful vertical teacher collaboration: A group process to create a K-12 articulated math program - ProQuest. (2016). Proquest.com. <https://www.proquest.com/openview/851cd667c47a623cf9f734443693a7c6/1?pq-origsite=gscholar&cbl=18750>
- Beilock, Sian L, & Willingham, D. T. (2014). Math Anxiety: Can Teachers Help Students Reduce It? Ask the Cognitive Scientist. American Educator, 38(2), 28. <https://eric.ed.gov/?id=EJ1043398>
- BERA https://www.deped.gov.ph/wp-content/uploads/2016/06/DO_s2016_039.pdf
- Bulgarian Journal of Science and Education Policy (BJSEP), Volume 14, Number 2, 2020
- DepEd Order No. 42, s. 2016 (Policy Guidelines on Daily Lesson Preparation for the K to 12 Basic Education Program):https://www.deped.gov.ph/wp-content/uploads/2016/06/DO_s2016_042.pdf
- DepEd Order No. 13, s. 2019 (Implementing Guidelines on the Utilization of Support to Operations Funds for Schools to Address Emergency and Unforeseen Expenses): https://www.deped.gov.ph/wp-content/uploads/2019/06/DO_s2019_013.pdf
- DepEd Order No. 9, s. 2020 (Institutionalization of the Results-Based Performance Management System): https://www.deped.gov.ph/wp-content/uploads/2020/06/DO_s2020_009.pdf
- DepEd Order No. 30, s. 2021: https://www.deped.gov.ph/wp-content/uploads/6-DO_s2021_030.pdf
- Dynamic Grouping in Collaborative Learning Supported by Wireless Handhelds on JSTOR. (2023). Jstor.org. <https://www.jstor.org/stable/jeductechsoci.8.3.149>
- NHERA: https://planipolis.iiep.unesco.org/sites/default/files/ressources/philippines_national_higher_education_research_agenda.pdf
- Professionalism in teaching and the role of teacher education. (2021). European Journal of Teacher Education. <https://www.tandfonline.com/doi/abs/10.1080/02619768.2020.1849130>
- UNESCO (2012). Challenges in Basic Mathematics Education. https://unesdoc.unesco.org/ark:/48223/pf0000191776_eng UN SDG <https://sdgs.un.org/goals>